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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“WE RISE AGAIN”

Life is tested, flooded with sorrow,
Sometimes we forget, the path to follow,
But in the heart, hope is hidden deep,
Even in darkness, light awaits to keep.

Tears may flow, like rain in the fall,
But behind them, a promise we won't fall,
The storm will pass, it won't last long,
For after the pain, light will come, rise again strong.

I will not allow fear to rule the chest,
I will not surrender to sorrow without rest,
For in my soul, the belief is ever strong,
After the darkness, light we'll gain, forever long.

This poem, a song of hope and might,
For the hearts, that are weary and contrite,
After the darkness, the light will arrive,
Let us remain strong, united to thrive